

Problems and Future Prospects in Marketing of Kota Doria

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ABSTRACT

The handloom sector is the largest economic activity after agriculture providing direct and indirect employment to more than 30 lakhs weavers. The handloom industries are environment friendly, energy saving form of artistry among the textile sector with the outcome of sustainable textile products. Indian handloom products are as different and varied as our cultures and languages. There may be many similarities in different styles, but then each handloom products are distinct from the other, has a mark of its own. This difference is in styles patterns or motifs used, ground fabric and yarns used. Each unique combination of weaves, motifs, patterns and colors conveys the historical experiences of the people who make and use it.

This study underlines the dynamics of handloom product at Kaithun and in the adjacent areas of Kaithun of Kota district in Rajasthan-Which is renowned in the field of weaving Kota Doria saree. In the present study, we have analyzed the emerging problems in marketing of Kota Doria sari of Kaithun in Kota district. The study is based on both the primary and secondary data sources. The study result reveals that the situation of the weavers of Kota Doria sari was pathetic and distressing due to illiteracy, financial constraints, health problems and poor government support.

Keywords: Handloom, Weavers, Kota Doria, Financial Constraints

INTRODUCTION:

The world handloom derives its meaning from the process of operation by hand of a country made wooden structure called loom. The handloom sector plays a very important role in India's economy. It is a part of our culture and heritage and one of the largest economic activities after agriculture having the capacity of absorbing a greater number of man powers.

The textile cottage industry includes cotton, silk, bleaching, dyeing, finishing, hosiery, lace, embroidery, silk reeling and silk twisting. It is the main source of livelihood of the people who absolutely depend on it.

Presently the handloom weavers are facing an uphill task for their survival because of unfavorable and pathetic attitudes of the government as well as globalization and changing socio-economic conditions. Moreover, there are so many issues which are impeding the development of the sector so it is highly needful to develop a wider understanding of its multi-disciplinary perspective which is now more necessary in the present day circumstances of globalization and environmental degradation particularly in relation to the development of handloom sector.

Kota Doria: Kota Doria is a world fame saree of Kota. The saree got the name because it belongs to Kota. It is famous for its light weight and simplicity. The saree is very comfortable to wear in summer season (there are almost 9 to 10 months when Indian face hot days). That is why Kota Doria is always in demand in whole India. Doria fabric was basically weaved in Mysore, Karnataka state. Shree Kishore

Singh, the king of Kota had the pit loom Doria fabric brought in 17th century from Mysore to Kaithun. Kaithun is 15km away from Kota. There are almost 2000-2500 looms and 10,000 families of the Kota Doria saree weavers.

The hypnotic and eye refreshing fabric of Kota Doria is made up of cotton and silk yarn in a different combination in warp and weft, which are woven in such a fashion and manner that they create square check patterns (Popularly known as Khat's). In the fabric, cotton and silk yarns of different thickness are used in weaving. The silk gives the necessary transparency and gossamer finish to fabric while cotton gives strength and firmness to the fabric (Charanji, 2007)¹.

The weavers living in Kaithun have to face many problems mainly related to their health, income, standard of living and unhygienic environments. The weavers of Kota Doria saree have no other income source other than weaving. That's why their standard of living is below level. The weavers also face health problem, such as backache, shoulder pain and problems related to vision after the age of 40-45 years.

People in Kaithun face financial problem if they want to set up any new business other than weaving. They should be given looms with lesser rate of interest by the banks. The mediators should not exploit the weavers in any way and they should help the weavers giving them latest knowledge and information from time to time. Kaithun appears to be a filthy place to live in. That's why the people live a poor and unhygienic life. Moreover, they do not have a good standard of life. Weavers are not aware of the way of modern marketing because only master weavers go for the marketing and the other aspirant weavers do not have adequate knowledge about the trends in the marketing. Of course some weavers of Kota Doria saree in Kaithun can earn some extra money by taking part in the fairs and exhibitions but they are unable to earn good money because of the want of 'Bunkar card'.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The primary objective of the present research work is to analyze the financial and marketing condition of the handloom weavers of Kaithun. The detailed objectives of this study are as followed:

- 1) To study various problems faced by the Kota Doria weavers.
- 2) To study the marketing issues faced by the weavers of Kota Doria saree.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Dantawala (1990)² The study shows the organizations of industrial weaver's co-operation society. Government implemented a scheme for the welfare of the society of the loom less weaver's large number of weavers without the loom are struggling hard under the control of master weavers on which they depend as there source of livelihood.

Doraiswamy (1996)³ In his study it is said that the handloom industry occupies the highest demand with better growth continuing process also it is difficult to find out the skilled labors to work on this sector the continuing demand cannot be matched by power looms in designs and texture.

Gurumoorthy (1995)⁴ He studied about the market development assistance to handloom cooperative societies, handloom fabrics are essential for the markets as well as for the overall administration of the handloom co- operatives' societies. The central government provides financial assistance to the handloom co-operatives for improving the marketing capabilities under market development assistance schemes

Rao and Sekhar (1998)⁵ In their study they focused on the issues related to weakness of handloom industry like the weak organizations, co-operatives, in adequate credits or finance no proper marketing infrastructure the situation had made it vulnerable

Research methodology: Research methodology may be understood as a science of studying how research is done scientifically. In it researcher adopt various steps in finding logic behind the problems. In this study both primary and secondary set of methods of data collection have been utilized and they have created valuable information to this research. To collect primary data field visit and interview of 40 respondents were taken and questionnaire was also asked. To collect secondary data, websites and external sources were utilized. In this study, both set of data collection have been utilized in the same emphasis. The data were analyzed by using simple bar diagram, pie diagram and questionnaire were asked

regarding , age, occupation, educational qualification, health problem, marketing, catalogues, raw material etc.

Analysis and interpretation of data: The data were collected from 40 satisfied random sample respondents by supplying the questionnaire. The data

were analyzed by using simple bar diagrams, pie diagrams on the bases of age wise, educational qualification, size of the family, income, assets owned major health ailment, no. of workers , awareness of various schemes and relationship between the production and sales.

According to, aforesaid table it is clear that 7.5% weavers belong to the age group between 15-25, 45% of the weaving community come in the age group between 26-35, 22.5% of the weavers come in the age group between 36-45, 20% of the weavers come in the age group between 46-55 and 5% of the weaving respondents come in the age group between 56-65.

From the above table it is clear that educational qualification of 7.5% weavers are illiterate, 52.5% weavers are educated up to secondary level, 17.5% up to senior secondary level, 22.5% graduation / post-graduation respectively.

From the above table it is obvious that in the marketing 50% master weavers are engaged, 2.5% weavers are in the field of designing, 7.5% in marketing and designing, 22.5% in marketing and weaving 17.5%weavers are in field of marketing designing and weaving.

From the above study and table it is obvious that 50% of the weavers have bunker identity card and remaining of the weavers do not have this card.

From the above table it is clear that 42.5% people associated in weaving have physical ailment, 2.5% do not have any physical trouble whereas remaining 55% are not directly indulged in the task of weaving and they are in the field of marketing or designing. So they do not have any physical ailment because of weaving.

From the above table it is clear that 35% weavers are associated with CFC, KDFC co-operative society remaining 57.5% weavers are not associated with any society, 7.5% remaining weavers did not respond.

The above table says that 100% of the respondents take 7 days to produce one plain saree, 85% of the respondents produce butidaar saree in 7- 15 days while remaining 15% respondents takes 15-20 days to produce butidaar saree. 57.5 % of the respondents takes 15-20 days according to the designs to produce an All over Kota Doria saree while 42.5% of the respondents takes 20-25 days to produce All over sarees. 70% of the respondents take 20-25 days to produce skirt-border Kota Doria saree while 30% of the respondents take more than 20-25 days to produce skirt-border Kota Doria saree.

87.5% of the respondents have not taken any training to use new technology in weaving Kota Doria saree but 12.5% of the respondents affirmed of having training in using new technology in the weaving of Kota Doria saree.

70% of the respondents affirmed that there was increase in the sale where as 30% of the respondents negated the increase in sale of Kota Doria saree.

85% of the respondents face big loss due to unsold stock of Kota Doria saree and 15% do not believe so.

62.5% of the customers come directly to Kaithun to purchase Kota Doria products where as 37.5% do not go to Kaithun for the purchase.

100% of the weavers of Kota Doria sarees do not have any catalogue.

From the above table it is apparent that the marketing of the weavers is diversified in many places in India as it is shown in the table. It is also to be noted that many single respondent have given multiple answers for single question that's why percentage is more than 100.

10% of the respondents find demand as the basis of their marketing, 5% of the respondents believe it to be the occasion, 10% of the respondents think season is the basis of their marketing but 75% of the respondents find that the main basis of their marketing is demand occasion as well as season.

From the above table it is clear that 7.5% respondents promote Kota Doria saree through fair, exhibitions, 2.5% through newspaper and 15% promote Kota Doria saree through Celebs ,7.5% other sources to promote Kota Doria saree and the remaining 67.5% of the respondents do not promote Kota Doria sarees.

From the above table it is clear that 80% of the respondents market and sell their products door to door, 17.5% of the respondents market their products on online website, 30% market and sell through Kota Doria retailing shops and 10% respondents market and sell their products in fairs and exhibitions.

42.5% respondents take part in fashion shows where as 55% of the respondents do not take any participation.55% respondents participate in exhibitions where as 42.5% of them do not, 22.5% of the respondents take part in national / international fairs where as 75% do not take part, 47.5% of the respondents take part in the melas (local) where as 50% of the respondents do not participate in the melas.

95% customers opt to pay cash payments while buying Kota Doria products. While 2.5% of customers opt to pay by using their credit card, 12.5% use internet banking while buying Kota Doria products, 7.5% customer use E-wallet for buying Kota Doria products 27.5% customers use other means (cheque etc.) for buying Kota Doria products.

The above table shows that the 12.5% respondents felt the problem of transportation, 25% of them felt the problem of delay in production, 10% of them felt the problem of limited stock and there were 57.5% of the respondents who felt some other problems like damage saree and product theft.

32.5% of the respondents feel that the ways of packaging affects the sale of product but 67.5% of them believe that the way of packaging does not affect the sale of product.

The aforesaid table shows 2.5% of respondents believe that it is the quality of material that fixes the price of products, 30% of respondents believe that it is the amount of work that fixes the price, 40% of respondents believe that it is the use of zari that fixes the price, 52.5% believe all these factors is responsible of fixing the price of the products.

17.5% respondents have link with online shopping apps and 82.5% respondents do not have any link.

10 % of the respondents find charges of labor responsible for the lesser margin of Kota Doria, 5% of them think the expensiveness of raw material is responsible, 2.5% of the respondents hold that the transportation charges are responsible for a lesser margin in the sale of Kota Doria saree, 30% of them believe that manufacturing process is costly but 55% of them stress all the above mentioned factors are responsible for the lesser margin in sale of Kota Doria.

100% respondents believe that Power loom is their real competitor, 47.5% of them also believed other handloom sarees responsible for the competition, 12.5% of them hold that designer’s fancy sarees are also putting up competition and 2.5% of the respondents believes other causes for the real competition.

2.5% of the respondents strongly disagree that the traditional way of marketing affects the sale of their products, 2.5% of the respondents disagree that the traditional way of marketing affects the sale of their products, 5% of them have no opinion regarding this, 40% of the respondents do agree that the traditional way of marketing affects the sale where as 50% of them strongly agree that the traditional way of marketing affects the sale.

2.5% of the respondents strongly disagree that with the adaptation of new technologies it will increase the sale, 2.5% of them disagree to this concept, 5% of them have no opinion regarding it where as 55% of the respondents agree that the demand and sale will increase with the adaptation of new technologies and 35% of the respondents strongly agree that if they adopt new technologies their sale increase.

10% of the respondents disagree that one of the reasons lesser sale of their product is that they are not able to take their product to the customers, 2.5% of them have no opinion regretting this where as 65% of the respondents agree that one of the reasons of lesser sale is that their product is not easily approachable to the customer and 22.5% strongly agree to this concept.

40% of the respondents strongly disagree that they do not prefer online shopping and 37.5% of that disagree to this concept. 15% of the respondents have no opinion regarding this, 5% of them agree to this concept of online shopping and 2.5% of the respondent strongly agree to this.

2.5% of the respondents have no opinion that the unsold stocks gets spoiled when kept for a longer period.60% of them agree to this concept and 37.5% of them strongly agree that the unsold stocks get spoiled when kept for a long period.

20%of the respondents agree that when they frequently show saree to the customer it gets damaged and 80% of them strongly agree to this concept.

77.5% customers demand for new product other than Kota Doria saree where as 22.5% customers do not demand for new products other than Kota Doria sarees.

17.5% of the customers prefer powerloom products because of their availability, 80% of them consider cost as the main reason behind it, 65% of the customer prefer powerloom products because of their unawareness, 25% of them prefer it because of its fast processing and 7.5% of the customers prefer it because of a cataloguing.

Noted Be: The responses are sometimes more than 100%. It is so because a different group of respondents are indulged in two or three department of the response.

Major findings and suggestions: This study underlines the major findings of the studies and suggestion for improving the marketing & financial condition of Kota Doria weavers at Kaithun in district of Kota Rajasthan. However, in due course of time there have been numerous unfavorable factors which led to the decline of this product Kota Doria. The decline of native enterprise, the unavailability and rising cost of raw material and cut throat competition from power loom are the other important factors which brought a fall in Kota Doria product.

There are various problems which the people living in Kaithun are facing. There is no source of income for them other than weaving of Kota Doria products. Most of the people living in Kaithun are in the same occupation and their income is not enough to start any other profession. That's why they have to face so many health problems during their task of weaving.

More over there is no 'Bunkar card' issued for the weavers in Kaithun because of which they face numerous problems. This is very useful for the weavers as this is required in fashion shows, exhibitions and fairs. These weavers use traditional types of marketing. They do not want to adopt new ways of marketing. They are not aware of the seasonal demand in Kaithun. Though Kota Doria product has acquired international fame but Kaithun is not into any exporters, boutiques and companies. They are selling Kota Doria products from door to door or/ and retail shops.

Very few people are associated with CFC (common facility center) which is a kind of a marketing committee situated at Kaithun but ironically the weavers are not educated and they are unaware of the latest trends of marketing. Their standard of understanding the latest technologies is meager and they are unable to get latest information about their business. Of course some of the weavers are apt and skilled but they are unable to earn enough income to keep their body and soul together, thus because of the lack of funds they are not able to send their children for good school and ultimately their children are also compelled to start their family business of weaving. So the vicious circle of lower living standard goes on incessantly and the weavers of Kota Doria saree remain poor throughout their lives.

Also, it is surprising that the weavers of Kota Doria saree are not aware about from where the raw material is brought and its price. The weavers of Kota Doria saree are not aware of marketing because marketing is done by the master weavers only. Thus, the weavers are unaware of market and selling price of incase if weavers prepare Kota Doria products without any order they do not get right value and even shopkeepers or retailers do not support them. The weavers urge to choose something different or other than weaving they cannot do this because of want of money or training or knowledge or other profession. So their financial condition does not permit them to improve their life style.

Health issues- Unhygienic livelihood and poor sanitary conditions prevailing at Kaithun, lead to unhealthy life. So it's the duty of government to arrange health camps for the betterment and good health of the residences of Kaithun. Physical checkup as well as eye camps should be started from time to time. At the same time proper training should be given to weavers to work in healthier conditions to accomplish their work well in time.

Exploitation of mediators –The master weaver and retail shopkeeper play the role of mediators among the weavers and customers and have lion's share. The mediators earn the maximum profit and the weavers get wages. In this way the weavers of Kota Doria saree are dependent on the master weavers and the shopkeepers for orders and thus mediators exploit the poor weavers of Kota Doria saree.

CONCLUSION

From the present study we conclude that the Kota Doria saree weavers at Kaithun and other weavers are in pitiable condition due to the poor socio economic conditions. The majority of them are poor, as their earning is very less in spite of working for more than 8 hours. a day. It is heart rending to note that almost 70% of the families of the weavers belong to low income group, obliged to work under middle man.

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